

CONDITIONS FOR DEVELOPING PRODUCTIVE SPEAKING COMPETENCE OF FUTURE ENGLISH TEACHERS

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Annotation. *This article provides information on improving the modern goals, content, and technologies of developing productive speech competence of future English language teachers, forming the methodology of teaching English in higher education, summarizing the traditional and foreign experiences accumulated in practice, and effectively organizing the educational process.*

Keywords: *education, English language, productive speech, competence, teacher, skill, educational process, communicative.*

Just as breathing is important for a person, communication also plays a significant role in his formation as a person. Through communication with others, humanity has reached the pinnacle of development. Without communication, there is no possibility of internal and external development of a person, his education and upbringing, and intellectual growth. Despite the fact that communication at first glance seems to be a simple concept, it is a complex and abstract process. There are various different interpretations of this concept in the literature, and representatives of various fields and sciences, including philosophers, psychologists, linguists, sociologists and cultural scientists, are engaged in this issue. As A.A. Leontiev noted, the main factor in the emergence of communication is vocabulary, that is, oral speech. Modern foreign language teaching methodology involves paying special attention to the development of oral speech at all stages of the continuous education system, in particular, in higher education. Today, the preparation of students for interethnic and intercultural relations, international cooperation, has been identified as an important priority task, which requires the development of students' oral and written speech skills and competences in the foreign language being studied.

The issue of the formation of linguistic skills in a foreign language was considered by world-renowned scientists P.Ya. Galperin, A.N. Leontyev, V.V. Vygotsky, N.I. Jinkin, I.A. Zimnyaya, Ye.I. Passov, A.A. Mirolyubov, R.P. Milrud, N.D. Galskova,

I. Gez, I.L. Bim, A. Buxbinder, P.B. Gurvich, A.N. Schukin and other specialists; teaching using information technologies was considered by such linguists as H. Reiders, E.S. Polat, R. Caudwell. Higher education is considered the foundation of the professional education system, the quality of student education depends on it, and this places great responsibility on the shoulders of future teachers. For a long time, higher education institutions in the education system were considered only as centers for providing theoretical knowledge. Today, they have radically changed their tasks and provide a comprehensive approach along with practical skills. At this stage, it is important to develop activity, independence, maintain cognitive activity and create conditions for the future teacher to enter the world of education, strengthen his health and emotional characteristics. Today, we are witnessing the development of these qualities of students with the introduction of ICT into the educational process. In our activities, we are introducing information technologies into the educational process, using them, and accumulating certain experience in using ICT in the educational process. Experience in the use of information technologies has shown that in cases of correct didactically use of ICT within the framework of a traditional lesson, unlimited opportunities arise for individualization and differentiation of the educational process.

In the educational process, significant changes occur, aimed at developing thinking and imagination as the main processes necessary for successful knowledge acquisition. Effective organization of students' cognitive activities is ensured. When using ICT, it is easy to implement a person-oriented approach in education, and it becomes possible to effectively organize the entire educational process. Multimedia educational programs, presentations, and projects were created using ready-made multimedia products and computer educational programs in the lesson process, and Internet tools in educational and extracurricular activities.

The task of English language teachers is not only to teach students or to focus more on their English language skills, such as reading, writing, listening and speaking, but also to help and inspire them by instilling a passion for English, a good attitude and strong motivation. Despite this, today, future teachers face a number of difficulties and obstacles in the formation of productive speech competence. These are:

1. Insufficient level of language proficiency of students. Some future teachers cannot speak English fluently, their lexical and grammatical knowledge is limited. This

significantly limits the ability to effectively teach the language they teach. According to Ye.I. Passov, how can a teacher teach students if he himself does not know the language well enough?

2. Fear of making speech errors. Students are afraid of making mistakes in public speaking activities (speaking in front of a special audience, presentations). This fear reduces their activity and slows down their speech development. As N.D. Galskova noted, fear of mistakes is the student's biggest enemy.

3. Difficulties in using innovative methods. Traditional grammar Students who have learned the ik-translation method have difficulty in using communicative methods, project-based learning and interactive technologies. E.S. Polat considers this problem as one of the most urgent problems of modern education.

4. Limited professional vocabulary. Most students know the words necessary for everyday communication, but are unaware of the special terms used in pedagogical activities. There is a need to develop bilingual vocabulary work on pedagogical terminology.

5. Limited use of personal computers and Internet technologies. The full use of ICT capabilities is not sufficiently supported, and skills in using special software and online platforms are not developed. According to H. Reiders, the use of information technologies in teaching is not only a modern requirement, but also a necessity.

6. The inextricability of the theoretical and practical parts of the educational process. Theoretical knowledge is taught without being combined with practice, which leads to difficulties for students in applying the acquired knowledge in real pedagogical activities. As J. Harmer noted, practice is the best teacher.

Learning difficulties	Teaching difficulties
▶ a disturbed classroom environment;	Learning difficulties ▶ it is very difficult to involve students in learning;
▶ large number of students in the classroom;	▶ it is difficult to manage students in the classroom;

▶ teaching resources are not enough for all students;	▶ limited teaching resources.
	▶ limited time.

Vocabulary, which is considered a component of linguistic competence, is the provision of language signs based on certain rules, based on the requirements of the expressed information and information flow, and is the result of psycho-physiological articulatory, socio-cultural activities. In linguistics, speech activity is studied as a product of language, while psychology considers it a speech process characteristic of a particular individual. Ye.I. Passov emphasizes the following in this process: "the priority aspect of linguistic competence is that through intonation, facial expressions and gestures the speaker can convey to the listener the nuances of the situation".

One of the effective ways to develop such skills is to overcome the difficulties of students in achieving the B2 level by using information technologies interactively in higher education institutions. Before choosing which method to use for teaching, the teacher should be ready to learn more about the main goals, objectives and responsibilities of teaching. In addition to preparation, teachers should also have acting skills. In other words, the teacher should be competent and competent in all areas, and teach in a unique and fluent way to convey knowledge.

Or, like a gardener watching plants grow, a teacher should support the student. Therefore, in order for students to understand the subject well, develop their readiness and knowledge, teachers should use appropriate teaching methods. In the process of language teaching, the use of teaching methods or techniques in the entire process of planning, selecting and evaluating how to teach language materials increases the effectiveness of the lesson. Therefore, it is considered effective to select methods based on the student's desires and skills, and to use them in the classroom taking into account the classroom context and the level of students. The specific teaching method and the selection of methods affect how the lesson is taught and the learning process. The time allocated for independent study outside of class and the correct creation of situations that test the acquired language knowledge outside the institution based on the instructions given by the teacher are also a task of the teacher's qualification.

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